

**FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF NGO'S – A CASE STUDY ON SKDRDP,
MANGALORE**

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Abstract

Finance is a lifeline of any business and NGOs are no exception. An organisation is only as operative as it has resources to meet its determination. Providing adequate resources is, primarily, the NGO board's responsibility. They need or contact and influence potentially large donors and otherwise monitor and guide fund raising initiatives. Active fund raising is one measure of the board's competences, obligation and influence. All organizations need money. with staff, money is the one thing that takes up most management time. By considering existing literature need is felt to study financial management of NGO's thus in this paper as concerned a case study of Sri Kshetra Dharmastala Rural Development Project (SKDRDP) is conducted by considering their financial management aspects. SWOT analysis is also done in this paper about general management and financial management in specific.

Key words: NGO's, Financial Management, SKDRDP

Introduction

NGOs are widely known for their social activities and community development. Three types of NGOs; Grass Roots Organisations (GROs), Support organizations, and Intermediary or Mid-level Organisations. Intermediary organizations operate for the welfare and development of the targeted segment of society through Grass Roots Organizations (GROs) or directly in the community and with the assistance of support organizations.

Presently, NGOs have taken the form of organizations as national or international institutions working outside the public administration of the country. The NGOs undertake developmental research, programme preparation and service delivery at the intermediate and local levels. The NGOs include various agencies and institutions such as cooperative, professional and social organisations, clubs and associations, research institutions, charitable, religious and neighbourhood groups throughout the country.

In the past, the word 'Management' was considered business management, but for NGOs, it was taken negatively in the sense of commercial operations. Since the last decade, NGOs themselves realized the importance of management, and the academicians along with NGO executives started thinking over the issues of vision, mission, strategic planning and overall management. However, the search for the definition of distinct management for this sector is underway. Much celebrated definition of democracy "Government of the people, by the people, for the people," seems fit to define NGOs after replacing the word 'Government' with 'Organisation' in this definition, because they are created on self-help basis, so it is of the people. People have links with it in the shape of recipients or donors of time, money, advice or anything else, so it is by the people. The accounting profession has either ignored the area entirely or has made excuses for inadequate reporting, specifically excluding nonprofits when accounting principles were promulgated. (Racek, 1988)¹

¹ Racek, T. J. (1988). Non-profit Accounting and Financial Reporting . In C. D. Tracy, *The non-profit Organisation Handbook* (pp. 6-3 to 6-46). McGraw-Hill Book company

NGO and Financial Management

Finance is a lifeline of any business and NGOs are no exception. An organisation is only as operative as it has resources to meet its purposes. Providing adequate resources is, primarily, the NGO board's responsibility. They need to contact and impact potentially large donors and otherwise monitor and guide fund raising creativity. Effective fund raising is one measure of the board's capabilities, obligation and influence. An NGO should be accountable for its actions and decisions not only to its funding agencies and the government, but also to the people it serves, its staff and members, partner organisations, and the public at large. (S, Bhargava, Radhakrishna, & Manivannan, 2007)²

Keeping Records:

The foundations of all accounting are basic records that define the earnings and spending. This means the contracts and letters for money you receive, the receipts, and the invoices for items that you buy. These elementary records prove that each and every operation has taken place. They are the cornerstones of being accountable.

Internal Control:

Some controls that are used include

- Keeping cash in a safe place (ideally in a bank account).
- ensuring that all expenditure is properly authorised.
- Following the budget.
- Monitoring how much money has been spent on what every month.
- Employing qualified finance staff.
- Having an audit every year.

SKDRDP (Shri Kshethra Dharmasthala Rural Development Project)

Shri Kshethra Dharmasthala Rural Development Project, popularly known as SKDRDP, is a charitable trust promoted by Dr D Veerendra Heggade. SKDRDP concentrates on the empowerment of rural women by organising Self-Help Groups (SHGs) on the lines of Joint Liability Groups (JLBs) of Bangladesh and provides infrastructure and finance through microcredit for the rural people.

During those dark days of the early 1980s, the SKDRDP extended support to the target groups enabling them to meet their basic needs. The message of the programme that the poor work hard to become self-dependent and self-reliant enlightened them. To provide them the initial stimulus for change and upliftment, the programme of Dharmasthala supplied necessary agricultural implements, guidance and support through Food-for work programme. All these encouragements went a long way in helping the poor agricultural families to cultivate their bits of land more efficiently and more intensively. Both the lessons of self-help and mutual-help imparted to them by the programme enabled them to find effective solutions to the intricate problems they were facing since centuries. A realisation dawned on them that a society can progress only if all individuals constituting it progress. It did not take much time for them to know that there is no substitute for hard work at all. The role played by Sevanirathas in awakening the rural masses in the area of operation of the programme was commendable.

What is strikingly important is the fact that the government departments connected with the task of rural development were approached by SKDRDP for contributing their mite to what was being done by Sevanirathas. Without entering any conflict or confrontation with the official agencies, SKDRDP succeeded in building basic rural infrastructure on which development in any region depends. The mobile dispensary of Sri Kshethra Dharmasthala helped the beneficiaries in a large measure. The message of 'planned parenthood' was taken to the doorstep of the beneficiaries who were burdened with large families before SKDRDP started.

Shri Kshethra Dharmasthala Rural Development Project encompasses all aspects of enriching rural life. It is currently engaged in developmental activities in Dakshina Kannada, Udupi, Uttara Kannada, Coorg, Shimoga, Chickmagalur, Dharwad, Haveri, Gadag, Tumkur, Belgaum, Mysore, Chamarnajagar, Koppal, Davangere, Chitradurga. Hassan, Mandya, Bangalore Rural, Bellary, Raichur and Bagalkote

² S, S., Bhargava, H., Radhakrishna, G., & Manivannan, J. K. (2007). "Accountability and Financial Transparency for NGOs": An Implementation. In S. S. Mishra, *NGO An Introduction* (pp. 32-46). Hyderabad: The Icfai University Press .

districts operating in 25,000 villages covering more than 28,19,500 families SKDRDP is active with its Community Development Programs throughout the state. During the year SKDRDP has extended its area of operation to six more districts viz., Hassan, Mandya, Bangalore Rural, Bellary, Raichur and Bagalkote.

SKDRDP® is registered under the Charitable Trust Act of 1920 in the office of Sub-Registrar, Government of Karnataka, Belthangady Taluk, Dakshina Kannada District in 1991.

SKDRDP began playing its role in the transfer of technology, providing infrastructure and providing finance through microcredit Besides, the project concentrated on the empowerment of rural women and hence began 'Jnanavikasa Program'. In response to the social needs of the area the SKDRDP innovated into activities like Janajagruthi, community development, Siri, etc.

A village-level worker known as 'Sevaniratha' would approach the stakeholder families, sit with them to prepare a five year development plan and assist them to implement the same. The Dharmasthala temple has given the required material support like equipment's, seed materials on a charity basis. In keeping with the HR policy of the organisation, the supervisory staff was promoted from the sevaniratha cadre in the prevailing areas. It has provided a great opportunity for youngsters to show their organisational skills in the new area.

To give opportunities to homemakers and unemployed young women in rural areas who have time and inclination to do social work, SKDRDP has developed a new cadre called the Sevaprathinidhi, who works in their spare time and support the SHG movement in the village. Most sevaprathinidh are women and have positively affected women man's ratio in the organisation.

Large quantities of rice were distributed during the initial decades as compensation for the families while they worked in their own lands, the concept of 'Food for Work' was implemented by SKDRDP, with a view to develop the lands. Thus, the initial decade of SKDRDP can be considered as the charity phase.

In the early 90s, on a review of the project, it was realised that mere charity does not give the desired result. Hence, SKDRDP adopted the self-help style by organising Self-Help Groups (SHGs), more on the lines of Joint Liability Groups (JLBs) of Bangladesh.

Review of Literature

There have been significant number of literature are found in the different areas of NGOs Financial Management all over the world.

Daniel Schewinger (2013) – Competition and strategy of Non-Governmental Organizations, in his study over 1200 NGOs associated with United Nations participated in the survey, where different mean values were found in the NGOs assessment of various dimensions and compition among NGOs of various budget sizes.

Hankin, Seidner and Zietlow (1998) found that in today's world characterised by competition, financial management of a non-profit organisation is just discouraging as that of a for profit organisation. Non-profit managers should have financial information which involves, managing an organisation's financial properties, creating and reviewing financial policies, accounting, budgets and financial reports, devoting for the short and long term and controlling and managing risk.

McLaughlin (2009) agrees that for financial purposes, a better way of looking at this industry is to sort it into categories according to the primary economic function the organisations perform. It is not sufficient to keep the financial records in order, but one must be able to validate good financial systems to meet all the other rising demands on today's non-profits.

Maddox (1999) finds that Budgeting is essential to non-profit management. In addition, budgeting is the one of the top tools existing to focus and establish an organisation.

Oster (1995) highlights that for many non-profits; fund raising is the most troublesome aspect of management. The budgeting structure and the financial reporting structure are as fundamental to planning and control in a non-profit as they are in a for-profit organisation.

Kingma (1993) underlines that each nonprofit organisation manager, in order to choose the correct level of revenue diversity, must consider the variance of all streams of revenue. Upcoming research must develop a formal model of the resources disbursed by non-profit organisation managers to secure funding.

Linzer & Linzer (2008) mentions that cash flow principles are pertinent to a wide variety of institutions, including nongovernmental organisations, religious institutions as well as other non-commercial entities that seek to provide benefits to society.

Zietlow & Seidner (2007) agree that non-profits may experience unique, challenging cash flow problems which can be solved using tools such as cash forecasting methods which will monitor cash flow dynamics and the cash position. In India, the term non-profit organisations are synonymously used with the term NonGovernmental Organisations.

Ravichandran (2007), states that in India, 86% of the nonprofit organisations/NGOs receive grants and contracts from the government and ODA. About three-fourths (71%) of non-profit organisations/NGOs have some income from donations and about 57% get community contributions.

Sooryamoorthy and Gangrade (2001) analyze that NGOs in India meaningfully contributed to the development-oriented initiatives, including empowerment of women and economically weaker sections of workers. Literature on financial management of NPO's in Indian context are very few and this area provides sufficient scope for researchers in India.

Statement of the Problem

By taking into consider above studies, financial Management is matter of alarm for NGO's and it directly affect the decision making process and fund raising. When financial management is done in the right way accountability to investors is possible and thus binds to more faith, thus in the light of above literature it is clear that there is need for study of Financial Management in NGO's and at the same time SKDRDP of Karnataka is more involved with micro finance and Self Help Groups so in this paper Financial Management of SKDRDP is taken as case for the study.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the need for Financial Management among NGO's in General
- To analyse the financial Management structure and Policies SKDRP
- To Study the financial Management and its strategies of SKDRDP

Research Methodology

This paper is focusing on the case study of SKDRDP, a NGO where financial data were gathered from published sources. The annual reports which is of secondary data and at the same to understand the existing research in the field. Thus books, journals and magazines are referred. On account of primary data discussions were held with NGO Manager and workers to understand the ground reality of keeping of books of accounts and reporting the same.

SKDRDP – FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT CASE STUDY

Table 1.1 Profile of SKDRDP

Address	The project office behind Vishnu enterprises, Falnir, Mangaluru
Name of the founder	Dr D. Veerendra Heggade
Year of Establishment	2002(Mangaluru)
Registration Detail	59/1991
Taluk/Districts -Locations	Above 20
Branches of the organisation	Local 76 Regional 28

Source: Internal Records

Table 1.2 Programmes and Special focus areas

PROGRAMMES	SKDRDP
Related to Education	4
Awareness programmes on Health	2
Self-employment & Vocational training	3
Sanitation and Hygiene	4
Women Empowerment	5
Awareness of human rights	2

Girl child Safety	5
Service for the old aged	6
Agriculture - support systems	1
Natural resource management	5

Source: Internal Records

While having discussions study found **SKDRDP** gives higher priority to Agriculture - support systems and have clear agenda of providing agricultural equipment on a affordable rental basis and this has achieved phenomenal success. Beyond this, they also provide small loans, Insurance and Pension to agriculturists and for women t under their microfinance programmes that study has referred under the head –“profiles of organizations”.

Table 1.3 Functioning of the Organisation

Frequency of Planning	Once in a year
Number of employees	
Top	2
Middle	30
Lower	30
Remuneration	
Top	Rs. 15,000 & Above
Middle	Rs. 10,000 & Above
Lower	Rs. 5,000 & Above
Method of communication	Personal Contact, Radio, News Paper, Posters, Announcement at the Temple
Invite people from other NGOs	Yes
Service training to employees	Yes
The duration of the training period	
Top	Less than one week
Middle	Less than one week
Lower	Less than one week

Source: Internal Records

As observed in **SKDRDP** it is once a year – it is possible to take financial budgeting and allocation of the same month wise, but in exigencies or to take advantage of government funding or urgent need of Recipients you can wait till the next year and looks impractical and may need revision in planning.

Table 1.4 Financial Plan

Capital outlay	Rs. 10 Lakh & above
Funds for the Activities	By founder/Loans/ Govt Schemes
Budget preparation	Yes
Nature of the budget	Yearly
If funds unavailable	Conduct the programmes with available funds
If stake holders disagree	Convince in favour of the programme

Source: Internal Records

The funds of the activities are raised

1. Loans
2. Donations by people
3. Government schemes
4. Founder contributions

The study found that **SKDRDP** is more proactive rather than being reactive when it comes to crunch of funds, they informed they go ahead with the project with available funds and keep the recipients necessity in mind.

SWOT Analysis

Organisational strategies are the means through which companies accomplish their missions and goals. Successful strategies address four elements of the setting within which the company operates and you must identify them in right earnest:

- The organisational strengths

- Organisational weaknesses
- The opportunities organisations foresee in its competitive environment
- The threat organisations may face in their competitive environment.

This set of four elements - strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats - when used by a firm to gain a competitive advantage, is often referred to as a “SWOT analysis”.

Strengths

- Committed staff
- Follow up/Focused Founders Direction
- Team Work

It is found that SKDRDP has committed staffs that are focused on the recipients of the programme benefits. They make them aware of the benefits, prepare necessary papers, fill them listening to recipients and follow up on government schemes. It found them work as a team, collaborating and cooperating with each other. What it found amazing is the staff’s willingness to listen and their patience to deal with most of the poor and low-income group of individual recipients.

It is also important to note that, people have great admiration towards the Founder and they are motivated by his involvement and praise they receive.

Weaknesses:

- No good linkage with government.
- Delayed decisions
- Employee attrition
- RBI Regulations on Fund Collections
- Gender Bias

It has a limitation to funds as recipients look for help or loans. Many times the fund crunch never allows them to expand their activities and this curtails their reach. Further, they talked RBI regulations on fund transfer, which has kept many donors away. They also talked about government interference in NGO activities.

They spoke about not having great linkage with government agencies. Government agencies do not disclose full details on schemes & programmes, which can benefit poor or target recipients for whom these schemes are drawn up.

They conveyed the constraint of taking decisions on urgent issues as they depend on their founders, the decisions are delayed, and recipients may not get help when needed.

They also spoke about employee Attrition. Qualified employees look for better wage and growth opportunities. NGOs have fund crunch may not be able to attract talent to remain with them as they cannot pay salaries what other commercial organisations pay. Additionally, they cannot expand as funds are a problem and people will not get promotions easily.

Female employees spoke about gender bias as far as involving them in decision-making process. It is observed this need to be addressed immediately by management as today women are equally competent and found to have multiple skills compared to men.

Opportunities:

- Enough local demands
- Cooperation
- Support from religious communities
- To conduct group activities
- New machines for agriculture

It is found that there are enough local demands and they must cash on them and make good of this opportunity.

It is found that they find great cooperation from their target recipient groups and this itself is a great opportunity for them to think innovative project for them in future.

It is found that great support came from their religious communities and found they are ready backup for furthering the projects and asking them to bring innovation in their projects.

It is found that new government initiatives and funding plans for agriculture and education sectors and they plan to mobilise their target members and create greater awareness in them to secure these facilities and get benefitted out of it.

SKDRDP find new opportunities in Agricultural sector and they have plans to buy more agricultural equipments like tractors, tillers etc which many of their target recipients wanted to hire during agricultural season as they cannot afford to own them.

Threats:

- Opposition
- Government interference

They feel a great opposition usually comes from the political class as many of their activities are for upliftment of poor and making them aware of their rights and seeking government intervention to alleviate their problems and the political class becomes the target of few protests undertaken. Like best example now Indian Government Vs India's farmers on Land acquisition bill.

They also feel RBI regulations on fund transfer, which has been keeping many donors away and it has hit them badly in their fund collections. They also talked about government interference in NGO activities, as reported in several newspapers at all India level; they feel government interference can come in the way of their growth and activities.

Financial Strategies NGOs can adopt to be more competent

Every NGO that participated in my study wanted to excel, be competent and grow. Organisational growth, and the demands of donors, however, is not the only reason for the pressure on NGOs to professionalise. NGOs must give more importance to the link between internal organisational capacities and their programme performance in the field and this can be achieved through their management style, the way they take decisions, strategic planning all these leads to success of projects they undertake.

In this study, it has suggested a method of four building blocks in efficient functioning of management of finances:

1. Keeping Records
2. Internal Control
3. Budgeting
4. Financial Reporting

The above will make the NGO organisation efficient and transparent and makes them to face any litmus test. Controlling and reporting appropriately about the financial activity makes an organisation efficient and wins the confidence of all stakeholders.

It also finds no difficulty in donors or any undue government interference if the NGOs in my study understand the laws of the land and act prudently, with a view that it should not create problem for the genuine donor. They must follow the Income tax rules as far as which is applicable and they need to be transparent as per FCRA 2010 rules.

Conclusion

NGOs need effective and accountable financial management for accountability and sustainability and it is a key component of program and organizational management. Yet, in many NGOs, the organisation's financial planning, controlling, monitoring, and reporting systems and how they are integrated into the overall organizational management process still needs strengthening. The world of NGOs is quickly changing, and progressively competitive. To be able to survive and develop, NGOs must have and implement quality financial management systems, which fulfil requirements for accountability, while strengthening the organisation's sustainability. Developing professional and strategic financial management will not only increase supporters' trust, it can also enhance an organisation's ability to manage their own resources for sustainability. Strategic planning, establishing internal controls, organising structure and responsibility, budgeting, preparing performance reports, financial reporting, cash flow analysis, etc. The increasing readiness of official funding for NGOs, the popularity they enjoy, and the increasing access they are offered to centres of national and international decision making

represent both an opportunity and a danger. As stated in (Edwards & Hulme, 2002)³ Globally, NGOs collect hundreds of billions of dollars annually from donors and distribute/utilise these funds to beneficiaries after paying for their own administrative costs. Openness is in the interest of the public, contributor organisations and authorities. However, the sheer volume of transactions conducted by NGOs combined with the desire not to overly burden legitimate organisations, underscore the importance of risk and size-based proportionality in making the suitable level of rules and overseeing in this area. (Bhargava, Radhakrishna & Manivannan, 2007)⁴. Financial accountability, transparency and good governance are the need of the hour in NGO's sector. It has been noted that as the financial and human resources employed in NGO's sector grow year after year, the need for proper financial planning, financial management and financial accountability is also increasing accordingly. (Kandasami, 2006)⁵. There have been long-ranging arguments regarding the financial accountability of the non-profits. Resource mismanagement is a specific problem with NGOs because the employees are unaccountable to anybody with a direct stake in the organization. An employee may start a new programme without revealing its complete liabilities. The employee may be rewarded for improving the NGO's image, making other employees happy, and appealing new donors.

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⁴ Bhargava, H., & Kumar, D. (2006). *NGO's: Role and Accountability-An introduction*. Hyderabad: The ICFAI University Press.(pp. 5 – 11)

⁵ Kandasami CA., M. (2006). *Role of Chartered Accountants in India's NGO Sector- An Emerging Opporutnity*. The Chartered Accountant.(pp 36 –52)